

Supplemental Material A

Survey of Implemented Mitigation Strategies and Further Needs of the United States Food Industry to Control COVID-19 in the Work Environment in Early 2021

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A Q5. Regarding control of COVID-19 in your industry sector, how concerning are the items below?

B Q7. Regarding the labor force needed to maintain the production capacity in your industry sector during the COVID-19 pandemic, how challenging are the items below?

Figure S1. Heatmaps representing responses to 5-point scale Likert questions regarding [A] concerns about COVID-19 control and [B] challenges to maintain production. These Likert questions were included in part 1 of the needs assessment survey asking general questions about a participant’s industry sector. For each item within a Likert question, a median shown to the right of the heatmap was calculated from the interval values (1-5), assigned to answers ranging from “Not at all concerning” to “Extremely concerning” [A] and “Not at all challenging” to “Extremely challenging” [B].

A Q9. Regarding needs to successfully mitigate COVID-19 in your industry sector, how important are the items below?

B Q11. If computational modeling tools were available to predict which COVID-19 mitigation strategies would most likely be successful in a given facility/operation at a given time, how important would the model features below be for your industry sector?

C Q13. Regarding indicators of successful responses to COVID-19 in your industry sector, how important are the items below?

Figure S2. Heatmaps representing responses to 5-point scale Likert questions regarding the [A] needs to successfully mitigate COVID-19, [B] preferred features in predictive models, and [C] indicators of a successful response against COVID-19. These questions were included in part 1 of the needs assessment survey asking general questions about a participant’s industry sector. For each item within a Likert question, a median shown to the right of the heatmap was calculated from the interval values (1-5), assigned to answers ranging from “Not at all important” to “Extremely important”.

A Q27. How would you describe the risk of a shutdown in this facility operation due to work absences in each of the specialized job functions below?

B Q29. Regarding potential sources of COVID-19 infection in this facility/operation, how concerning are the items below?

Figure S3. Heatmaps representing responses to 5-point scale Likert questions regarding [A] the risk of shut down due to absenteeism of employees with specialized job functions and [B] sources of COVID-19 in the work environment. These Likert questions were included in part 1 of the needs assessment survey that asked about conditions and COVID-19 controls in a facility or operation of a participant’s choice. For each item within a Likert question, a median shown to the right of the heatmap was calculated from the interval values (1-5), assigned to answers ranging from “No risk” to “Very high risk” [A] and “Not at all concerning” to “Extremely concerning” [B].

TABLE S1. All questions (Q) included in the needs assessment survey, question type, type of analysis (statistical or thematic) and role in statistical analysis of associations (as an outcome of interest (primary or secondary) or independent variable (predictor)). Responses considered usable for analysis were those in which participants completed at least part 1 of the needs assessment survey.

Q	Question	Question type	Analysis type ^a	Role in statistical analysis ^b
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Levels/Likert scale items 			
Part 1: General questions about a participant's industry sector				
1 ^c	What industry sector are you in? (select all that apply) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fresh produce; Dairy; Beef/Pork; Poultry; Other 	Multiple-choice	S	P
2 ^c	Select your main role within your organization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> C-suite; Regional manager; Facility manager; Research and development; Corporate food safety and quality; Other; Prefer not to answer 	Single-choice	S	P
3	Did COVID-19 have a significant impact on your industry sector? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes; No 	Single-choice	S	P
4	In which way(s) has COVID-19 significantly impacted your industry sector? (select all that apply) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operations/production has been reduced/cut back; Operations/production has expanded; Implemented robotics, sensors, automation, and/or computer modeling; Management/corporate employees working remotely; Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols 	Multiple-choice	S	P
5	Regarding control of COVID-19 in your industry sector, how concerning are the items below? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizational awareness of the virus; Labor availability; Workers' compliance with control measures; Workers' abuse of control measures; Limited financial resources; Production capacity; Product quality; Supplier management; Customer expectations; Complex/ever-changing government regulations about COVID-19 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Os
6	Regarding control of COVID-19 in your industry sector, are there any other concerns we should consider?	Open-ended	T	N/A
7	Regarding the labor force needed to maintain the production capacity in your industry sector during the COVID-19 pandemic, how challenging are the items below? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to number of workers needed; Access to workers with necessary skills; Sufficient housing for labor; Turnover in workforce; Need to train labor 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Os
8	Regarding the labor force needed to maintain the production capacity in your industry sector during the COVID-19 pandemic, are there any other challenges we should consider?	Open-ended	T	N/A
9 ^c	Regarding needs to successfully mitigate COVID-19 in your industry sector, how important are the items below? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> More and better training; Training materials in more languages; Better technologies to assure social distancing; Better and cheaper testing technologies; Easier way to understand regulations; Better information on cost effectiveness of COVID-19 mitigation strategies 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Op
10	Regarding needs to successfully mitigate COVID-19 in your industry sector, are there any other important needs we should consider?	Open-ended	T	N/A

11 ^c	If computational modeling tools were available to predict which COVID-19 mitigation strategies would most likely be successful in a given facility/operation at a given time, how important would the model features below be for your industry sector? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Ability of the model to predict impact on production capacity; Ability of the model to predict initial and ongoing cost of implementation; Ability of the model to predict infection risk reduction; Ease of model use by company personnel; Ability to use the model confidentially; Ability to customize the model for use in a specific facility</i> 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Op
12	Regarding a potential modelling tool that could predict successful COVID-19 mitigation strategies, are there any other model features important for your industry sector we should consider?	Open-ended	None	N/A
13 ^c	Regarding indicators of successful responses to COVID-19 in your industry sector, how important are the items below? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Workforce trained about COVID-19 risks and mitigation; Standard operating procedures/checklists are in place for mitigation of COVID-19 impacts; Established effective risk communication plan; Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation; Investment made into technologies that reduce vulnerability to a future pandemic or similar system wide disruption; Workforce related contingency plans updated to minimize COVID-19 related business interruptions</i> 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Op
14	Regarding attainable indicators of successful responses to COVID-19 in your industry sector, are there any other important indicators we should consider?	Open-ended	None	N/A
Part 2: Conditions and COVID-19 controls in a facility or operation of participant's choice				
15 ^c	In what industry sector is this facility/operation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Fresh produce; Dairy; Beef/Pork; Poultry; Other</i> 	Single-choice	None	N/A
16	How does this facility/operation operate? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Year-round; Seasonally</i> 	Single-choice	S	P
17	What are the approximate start and end dates for the production season(s) in this fresh produce facility/operation?	Open-ended	S	P
18	What role best describes this facility/operation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Grower; Packing House; Processor; Grower and Field packer; Grower and Processor; Other</i> 	Single-choice	S	P
19	Please select which part of your Grower and Processor operation will you describe in the remaining questions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Grower operation; Processor facility</i> 	Single-choice	S	P
20	What was the average number of employees in this facility/operation in 2019? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Less than 10; 10-49; 50-99; 100-249; 250-499; 500-999; 1000-2000; More than 2000; This facility/operation did not operate in 2019; Prefer not to answer</i> 	Single-choice	S	P
21	What is the approximate proportion (%) of employees in this facility/operation that are between 50-69 years of age and 70 years old or older?	Open-ended	S	P
22	Does this facility/operation provide group temporary (seasonal) housing to any of your employees? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Yes; No</i> 	Single-choice	S	P
23	Approximately what proportion (%) of employees in this facility/operation are provided with group temporary housing?	Open-ended	S	P
24	Does this facility/operation provide group transportation services (bus, truck, etc.) to employees to/from work?	Single-choice	S	P

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Yes; No</i> 			
25	Approximately what proportion (%) of employees in this facility/operation are provided with group transportation to/from work?	Open-ended	S	P
26 ^c	What is the largest percent reduction in the general production labor force that this facility/operation could withstand over a period of one week without reduction in the production capacity? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>5%; 10%; 15%; 20%; 30%; 40%; 50%; Do not know</i> 	Single-choice	S	Op
27	COVID-19 related work absences among workers performing different specialized job functions in this facility/operation present different levels of risk for a facility/operation shutdown. How would you describe the risk of a shutdown in this facility/operation due to work absences in each of the specialized job functions below? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Specialized production line functions (for example, operators for specialized equipment); Lab personnel; Quality control and assurance; Sanitation and cleaning; Supervisors; Engineering and/or maintenance crew</i> 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Os
28	Regarding the risk of a shutdown in this facility/operation due to work absences, are there any other specialized job functions we should consider?	Open-ended	None	N/A
29	Regarding potential sources of COVID-19 infection in this facility/operation, how concerning are the items below? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Employee housing conditions; Employee transportation conditions; Indoor common areas (for example, restrooms, breakrooms, personal protective equipment area, offices); Outdoor common areas; Common production tools/equipment; Production line; Activities in the local community</i> 	5-point scale Likert question	S	Os
30	Regarding potential sources of COVID-19 infection in this facility/operation, are there any other concerns we should consider?	Open-ended	None	N/A
31	If in the future the available labor force in this facility/operation is affected by a COVID-19 outbreak, what short/mid-term solutions should be considered to maintain production? (check all that apply) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Extend the number of work hours for remaining workers; Backfill with emergency personnel from third-party companies; Backfill by reorganizing personnel in the same facility</i> 	Multiple-choice	S	P
32	To prevent labor shortage in this facility/operation due to a potential future COVID-19 outbreak, should capital investment into mechanization be considered as a long-term solution to maintain production? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Yes; No</i> 	Single-choice	S	P
33	To maintain production in the event of labor shortage in this facility/operation due to a potential future COVID-19 outbreak, are there any other solutions we should consider?	Open-ended	T	N/A
34	Have any of these social distancing strategies been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Installed physical barriers; Staggered break times; Staggered arrival/departure times (staggered shifts); Downsizing operation; Adjusted sick day policy; Spacing workers >6ft during production; Cohorting employees</i> 	3-point scale Likert question	S	Op
35	For one or more of these social distancing strategies, could you share any reasons for adopting or not adopting it, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information?	Open-ended	T	N/A
36	Have any of these employee biosafety strategies been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?	3-point scale Likert question	S	Op

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced handwashing; Alcohol-based hand rubs; Face mask, face shields, goggles; Increased ventilation rates; Air cleaning/filtering 			
37	For one or more of these employee biosafety strategies, could you share any reasons for adopting or not adopting it, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information?	Open-ended	T	N/A
38	<p>Have any of these surveillance strategies been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature screening and quarantine; Test for infection and isolation; Contact tracing and quarantine; Return to work post recovery policy 	3-point scale Likert question	S	Op
39	For one or more of these surveillance strategies, could you share any reasons for adopting or not adopting it, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information?	Open-ended	T	N/A
40	What is this Other mitigation strategy? Please specify.	Open-ended	None	N/A
41	<p>Has this Other mitigation strategy been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes; Yes, but only partially/ temporally; No 	3-point scale Likert scale question	None	N/A
42	Could you share any reasons for adopting or not adopting this Other strategy, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information?	Open-ended	None	N/A
43 ^c	<p>What was the main reason for your choice to describe conditions and COVID-19 mitigation in this particular food production facility/operation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am mostly familiar with this facility/operation; This is our unique facility/operation; This is our typical facility/operation; This facility/operation has been impacted greatly by COVID-19; This is our strategically important facility/operation; Other 	Single-choice	S	P

^aAnalysis type: S=statistical analysis; T=thematic analysis; None=responses were examined but not systematically analyzed

^bRole in statistical analysis: Op=primary outcome; Os=secondary outcome; P=predictor; N/A=not applicable

^cParticipants were required to answer the question to continue the needs assessment survey.

TABLE S2. Themes and underlying codes identified in participants’ responses to selected open-ended questions in the needs assessment survey, which were intended to provide depth to the corresponding Likert questions. An example quote is included to illustrate each of the codes identified.

Likert question	Corresponding open-ended question (Number (N) responses)	Theme	Code	Quote	Participant’s info	
					Industry sector	ID
Q5	Q6, Regarding control of COVID-19 in your industry sector, are there any other concerns we should consider? (N=19)	Access to COVID-19 preventative measures, guidance and information; difficulties in implementation of mitigation strategies	PPE shortage	Costs and the availability for PPE	Fresh produce	40
			Vaccine access	Having vaccines available to our workforce. Being able to work with local agencies and providers to pre-arrange an on-site Covid-19 vaccination for our employees, much like flu vaccines are available. We encourage our employees to get vaccinated when they become eligible, however, it is so complex to try to arrange for an appointment, we are extremely concerned that our employees will not get vaccinated even when the vaccine is available to them.	Dairy	11
			COVID-19 misinformation	Cultural attitudes/disinformation [about the] existence of the virus	Other (prepared food)	51
			Difficulties in implementation of mitigation strategies	The bigger the food producer, the more likely to observe failures in preventative controls, including risk-reduction measures for Coronavirus SARS-II exposure and cross-transmission to fellow coworkers. Inspecting facilities for Food Safety issues also has exposed continual, chronic GMP and pre-requisite issues (including effective sanitation).	Other (fresh produce, dairy, beef/pork, and poultry)	72
		Employee fatigue, vaccine hesitancy, health and healthcare access	Lack of COVID-19 guidance	Lack of industry specific guidance for food industry masking, face shields, and combo use.	Dairy	71
			Employee fatigue	Employee (front-line production) fatigue.	Dairy	29
			Vaccine hesitancy	Implementing vaccination programs with a somewhat resistant labor force	Fresh produce	46
			Employee health	Mental health impact on managerial and office staff. In talking with industry colleagues, my experience is that many facilities have cut back on the staff responsible for ensuring that the facility is operating in an efficient and structured manner, while expanding the production capacity of the facility. It leaves many of these employees in a position where they are stretched thin and feel overwhelmed. Conversely, many facilities are putting policies in place to improve the	Other (co-packaging of shelf stable products)	75

				quality of life for hourly workers to try to attract and keep workers in an environment where it is hard to find new workers at wage rates that previously attracted workers.		
			Employee healthcare access	Transient work populations working in remote areas with limited public health resources	Other (sea-food)	76
		Supply chain disruption and management of contractor expectations	Supply chain disruption	Ability of suppliers upstream of us.	Dairy	56
			Management of contractor expectations	Contractor control measures are difficult to manage.	Dairy	16
Q7	Q8, Regarding the labor force needed to maintain the production capacity in your industry sector during the COVID-19 pandemic, are there any other challenges we should consider? (N=20)	Government benefits and regulations, guidance documents, and other requirements	Government benefits for unemployed	Easily obtainable government handouts have a negative effect on those willing to participate in the labor market	Dairy	9
			Changing government regulations, guidance documents, and other requirements	Government directives and laws regarding labor, time off, and pay rules and the changes in these made managing government special rules a full time job, rather than managing the pandemic we were managing the labor law compliance tasks.	Fresh produce	45
		Downside of COVID-19 mitigation strategies	Downside of mitigations	Because of social distancing, infrastructure is not enough to keep the amount of people we need to reach our production goals	Fresh produce	42
				Housing and transportation of workforce to enable safe social distancing during the pandemic and contact tracing reducing large portions of the normal workforce in quick succession	Fresh produce	46
		Labor availability, needs, expectations and behavior	Inability to hire skilled labor	Finding a qualified temporary work force.	Dairy	15
			Employee behavior	Employees getting, spreading, being exposed to the virus.	Other (food services)	39
			Reliance on critical employees	When someone is out of the workplace sick it is incredibly difficult to manage for small businesses	Other (food processing)	58
			Bias in hiring minorities	Recent events in Minneapolis have shown the difficulties certain minorities group face and this is pushing the industry to reevaluate the recruiting process to ensure unbiased hiring practices.	Other (spirits)	62

			Unacceptable employee expectations	Expectation of pay. In Northern NJ, average pay expectation has increased as Amazon offers close to 20 an hour for minimally skilled labor. Grocery stores are also offering close to 15 for the same. There are many food facilities who were previously between 11 (state minimum) and 15 an hour for unskilled labor. Customers aren't always willing to accept price increases. So it is a balance of splitting increased labor costs with customers, which makes thin margins thinner.	Other (co-packaging of shelf stable products)	75
			Employee support services	Transportation. Childcare	Fresh produce	65
			Employee language barriers	Multi language barriers	Other (seafood)	76
Q9	Q10, Regarding needs to successfully mitigate COVID-19 in your industry sector, are there any other important needs we should consider? (N=8)	Consumer education	Consumer education	In regards to food industry, zero cases food to people, people to food must be communicated to public	Fresh produce	60
		Technology to improve infection prevention, time efficiency and internet access	Technology to reduce infection exposure	More technology to reduce exposure and maximize time efficiency	Fresh produce	42
			Technology to improve time efficiency	More technology to reduce exposure and maximize time efficiency	Fresh produce	42
			High-speed Internet	Remote areas with little to no internet makes training and communication difficult	Other (seafood)	76
		Cost-effective mitigation strategies, harmonized guidance and prioritized vaccination of food industry workers	Harmonized guidance about COVID-19 control	Consider that during the CV-19 pandemic businesses have received directives and policy recommendations and requirements from: Federal, state, and local governments, industry trade associations, our insurance company, food safety consultants, legal teams, auditors. All with different recommendations...none of them were right...ridiculous We've turned the pandemic into a new industry.	Fresh produce	45
			Assistance to small-to-medium-sized businesses	Better support for small to medium sized farms/companies, including expansion of extension resources.	Other (unspecified ^a)	50
			Cost-effective mitigation strategies	No [return of investment] ROI assessments have been made in effective mitigation techniques; their have been no incentives to implement mitigation techniques; no enforcement on simple requirements led many not to implement effective measurements	Other (spirits)	62

			Prioritized food worker vaccination	Vaccination of "front-line" clinical workers needs to also be re-prioritized to include all of the front-line food handlers.	Other (fresh produce, dairy, beef/pork, and poultry)	72
Q32	Q33, To maintain production in the event of labor shortage in this facility/operation due to a potential future COVID-19 outbreak, are there any other solutions we should consider? (N=9)	Employee benefits and training	Employee benefits	If extending the number of work hours for remaining workers, compensate with double time for hours worked past 40, Start OT after scheduled hours worked daily instead of after 40 hours	Dairy	8
		Industry collaboration, production adjustment and infrastructure changes	Collaboration across industry	Possibly organize and facilitate an exchange program amongst dairy processing companies to support one another with qualified workers.	Dairy	9
			Adjust production	Reduction of the complexity of [Stock Keeping Unit] SKU offerings to maximize efficient production and maximize limited offerings at higher volumes to all customers	Fresh produce	46
			Infrastructure changes	Enlarging employee common areas.		56
Q34	Q35, For one or more of these social distancing strategies, could you share any reasons for <u>not adopting</u> it, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information? (N=12)	Infrastructure, productivity or Union imposed constraints	Infeasible due to infrastructure limitations	Space considerations have been implemented but there are occasions which plant design does not allow 100% effectiveness. We mitigate by changing production schedules and staggering production to limit number of employees in close contact while on the floor	Fresh produce	46
			Negative impact on productivity	If the plant does not run near full production, we are out of business.	Dairy	56
			Union imposed constraints	We are unable to downsize due to connection with farmers. Cohorting due to union contract constraints.	Dairy Dairy	9 30
			No improvements applicable	We do not have enough employees to make staggering shift a possible solution	Other (food processing)	58
		Lack of concern or need	Lack of concern	All employees are very diligent in following the rules, so We do not feel we need to worry as much	Other (manufacturing shelf-stable foods)	63
			No improvements required or applicable	We are small and family the of the four have been vaccinated.	Fresh produce	59
		Q36	Q37, For one or more of these biosafety		Unavailable supplies	Availability of supplies at the onset but now you need to monitor the reliability of the products for compliance.

	strategies, could you share any reasons for <u>not adopting</u> it, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information? (N=10)	Lack of funds, supplies or information	Cost of implementation	We felt the cost of a new or upgraded ventilation system was not justified with all of the other precautions already in place.	Other (manufacturing shelf-stable foods)	63
Lack of information on effectiveness			Leadership not willing to make decisions, no CDC guidance on benefits for doing more than normally done. Mask usage yes, face shields no due to no CDC guidance for combo. No advisement on managing ventilation and filtering	Dairy	71	
Infrastructure constraints		Infeasible due to infrastructure limitations	Increased ventilation is applied when possible but the nature of our production requires controlled environment inside the building. Air filtering is not as practical in a short term implementation -we use positive air in high density work areas	Fresh produce	46	
Lack of need		No improvements required or applicable	Plant air is already highly filtered with turnover every 20 minutes, so no change there.	Dairy	56	
Q38	Q39, For one or more of these surveillance strategies, could you share any reasons for <u>not adopting</u> it, such as cost, compliance by workers, training requirement, effectiveness in reducing health risks, impact on production capacity, and/or lack of science-based information? (N=10)	Lack of concern or need	Lack of concern	We all have been and continue to be very careful and healthy.	Other (manufacturing shelf-stable foods)	63
			No improvements required or applicable	Good community testing access so no reason to bring on site	Dairy	30
		Increases worker absences	Increases work absences	No funding available.	Dairy	56

^aAcademic affiliated with the food industry.

TABLE S3. Significant associations found in the bivariable analyses ($P \leq 0.05$) using Mann-Whitney U (MW-U) and Spearman's correlation (SC) tests between a specific Likert item (outcome) in a survey question (Q) and independent variables (predictors).

Likert question (Q) ^a - Item	Predictor	Statistical test	Level	Median ^b /correlation ^c	IQR ^b	<i>p</i> -value
Q5, Regarding control of COVID-19 in your industry sector, how concerning are the items below?						
- Limited financial resources	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	3	2-4	<0.001
			Yes	1	1-2	
- Limited financial resources	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	2	1-3	0.02
			Yes	3	2-4	
- Limited financial resources	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Implemented robotics, sensors, automation, and/or computer modeling	MW-U	No	2	2-3.25	0.04
			Yes	4	3-4	
- Limited financial resources	Q31, Short mid solutions to maintain production: Extend the number of work hours for remaining workers	MW-U	No	4	2-4	0.03
			Yes	2	1.25-3	
- Limited financial resources	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	2	2-3	0.02
			Yes	4	3-4	
- Complex/ever-changing government regulations about COVID-19	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	3-5	0.02
			Yes	3	3-4	
- Complex/ever-changing government regulations about COVID-19	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	3	3-4	0.04
			Yes	4	3-5	
- Workers' compliance with control measures	Q23, Proportion (%) of employees with group temporary housing	SC	N/A ^d	-0.81 ^c	N/A	0.03
- Workers' compliance with control measures	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.85 ^c	N/A	0.02
- Customer expectations	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.03
			Yes	2	2-3	
- Customer expectations	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	2	1-3	0.005
			Yes	3	2-4	
- Customer expectations	Q31, Backfill by reorganizing personnel in the same facility	MW-U	No	2	1.75-3	0.02
			Yes	3	2-4	
- Organizational awareness of the virus	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.85 ^c	N/A	0.02

Q7, Regarding the labor force needed to maintain the production capacity in your industry sector during the COVID-19 pandemic, how challenging are the items below?							
- Access to workers with necessary skills	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	2.5	2-3.25	0.04	
			Yes	4	3-3.45		
- Sufficient housing for labor	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Implemented robotics, sensors, automation, and/or computer modeling	MW-U	No	2	1-3	0.001	
			Yes	4	4-4		
- Sufficient housing for labor	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	2	1-3	0.004	
			Yes	4	3-5		
- Sufficient housing for labor	Q21, Proportion (%) of employees 70 years or older ^e	SC	N/A	0.40 ^c	N/A	0.004	
Q9, Regarding needs to successfully mitigate COVID-19 in your industry sector, how important are the items below?							
- Better information on cost effectiveness of COVID-19 mitigation strategies	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	3-4	0.005	
			Yes	3	2-3.5		
- Training materials in more languages	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.002	
			Yes	1	1-2.5		
- Training materials in more languages	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	2	1-2	<0.001	
			Yes	4	2-4		
- Training materials in more languages	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	2	1-4	0.02	
			Yes	5	3-5		
- Better and cheaper testing technologies	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	3-5	0.02	
			Yes	3	2-4		
- Better and cheaper testing technologies	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.002	
			Yes	4	3-5		
- Better and cheaper testing technologies	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.03	
			Yes	5	3-5		
- More and better training	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.02	
			Yes	4	3-5		
- More and better training	Q24, Group transportation provided to employees	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.02	
			Yes	4	4-5		
- Easier way to understand regulations	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	3-5	0.03	
			Yes	3	2-4		

- Easier way to understand regulations	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	2.5	2-3.75	0.008
			Yes	4	3-5	
- Better technologies to assure social distancing	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.78 ^c	N/A	0.04
- Better technologies to assure social distancing	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	3	2-3	0.01
			Yes	4	2-4	
Q11, If computational modeling tools were available to predict which COVID-19 mitigation strategies would most likely be successful in a given facility/operation at a given time, how important would the model features below be for your industry sector?						
- Ease of model use by company personnel	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	3-5	0.003
			Yes	3	3-4	
- Ability to customize the model for use in a specific facility	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	4-5	0.007
			Yes	3.5	3-4	
- Ability of the model to predict infection risk reduction	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	4	3-5	0.03
			Yes	3.5	3-4	
- Ability of the model to predict initial and ongoing cost of implementation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	3	2.75-4	0.02
			Yes	4	3-5	
Q13, Regarding indicators of successful responses to COVID-19 in your industry sector, how important are the items below?						
- Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	3.5	3-4	0.02
			Yes	3	2-3	
- Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	3	2-3	0.04
			Yes	4	3-4	
- Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Implemented robotics, sensors, automation, and/or computer	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.05
			Yes	4	4-4	
- Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	2	2-3	0.04
			Yes	3	3-4	
- Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.88 ^c		0.009
		MW-U	No	4	3-5	0.03

- Digital technologies utilized in planning of facility specific COVID-19 mitigation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded		Yes	3	2-4	
- Workforce trained about COVID-19 risks and mitigation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	4	3-4	0.03
			Yes	4	4-5	
- Standard operating procedures/checklists are in place for mitigation of COVID-19 impacts	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	4	3-4	0.03
			Yes	4	4-5	
- Established effective risk communication plan	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	3	3-4	0.007
			Yes	4	4-5	
- Workforce related contingency plans updated to minimize COVID-19 related business interruptions	Q31, Backfill by reorganizing personnel in the same facility	MW-U	No	3	2.75-4	0.02
			Yes	4	3.75-5	
Q27, COVID-19 related work absences among workers performing different specialized job functions in this facility/operation present different levels of risk for a facility/operation shutdown. How would you describe the risk of a shutdown in this facility/operation due to work absences in each of the specialized job functions below?						
- Sanitation and cleaning	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	3	2-3.75	0.01
			Yes	4	3-5	
- Lab personnel	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	2.5	2-3	0.03
			Yes	3	3-4	
- Lab personnel	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	-0.90 ^c	N/A	0.02
- Supervisors	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	3	2-3	0.02
			Yes	3	3-4	
- Engineering and/or maintenance crew	Q21, Proportion (%) of employees from 50 to 69 years ^e	SC	N/A	0.27 ^c	N/A	0.04
Q29, Regarding potential sources of COVID-19 infection in this facility/operation, how concerning are the items below?						
- Activities in the local community		MW-U	No	2	1-3	<0.001

		Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols		Yes	4	3-5	
-	Indoor common areas (for example, restrooms, breakrooms, personal protective equipment area, offices)	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	3	2-4	0.02
				Yes	4	3-5	
-	Common production tools/equipment	Q31, Backfill by reorganizing personnel in the same facility	MW-U	No	2	1.75-3	0.03
				Yes	3	2-4	
-	Common production tools/equipment	Q21, Proportion (%) of employees from 70 years or older ^e	SC	N/A	0.32 ^c	N/A	0.02
-	Production line	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	2	1.5-2.5	0.01
				Yes	3	2-4	
-	Production line	Q24, Group transportation provided to employees	MW-U	No	3	2-3	0.04
				Yes	4	2.75-4	
-	Employee housing conditions	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	3	1-4	0.04
				Yes	1	1-2	
-	Employee housing conditions	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	1	1-2	0.03
				Yes	2.5	1-4	
-	Employee housing conditions	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	1	1-3	<0.001
				Yes	4	3-5	
-	Employee housing conditions	Q24, Group transportation provided to employees	MW-U	No	1.5	1-3	0.02
				Yes	3.5	2.75-3.5	
-	Employee transportation conditions	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	1	1-2.5	0.05
				Yes	2	1-4	
-	Employee transportation conditions	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	1	1-1	0.002
				Yes	2.5	1-4	
-	Employee transportation conditions	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	1.5	1-3	0.002
				Yes	4	3-5	
-	Employee transportation conditions	Q24, Group transportation provided to employees	MW-U	No	1	1-3	0.007
				Yes	3.5	2.75-4.25	
-	Outdoor common areas	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	1	1-1.5	0.01
				Yes	2	1-3	
-	Outdoor common areas	Q21, Proportion (%) of employees from 70 years or older ^e	SC	N/A	0.27 ^c	N/A	0.05

- Outdoor common areas	Q24, Group transportation provided to employees	MW-U	No	1	1-2	0.005
			Yes	3	2-4	
Q34, Have any of these social distancing strategies been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?						
- Downsizing operation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	0	0-0.5	0.004
			Yes	0	0-0	
- Downsizing operation	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has been reduced/cut back	MW-U	No	0	0-0	0.002
			Yes	0	0-0.5	
- Downsizing operation	Q22, Temporary housing provided to employees	MW-U	No	0	0-0	0.003
			Yes	0.5	0-0.5	
- Downsizing operation	Q21, Proportion (%) of employees from 70 years or older ^e	SC	N/A	0.31 ^c	N/A	0.02
- Downsizing operation	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.88 ^c	N/A	0.009
- Adjusted sick day policy	Q23, Proportion (%) of employees with group temporary housing	SC	N/A	-0.76 ^c	N/A	0.05
- Staggered arrival/departure times (staggered shifts)	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	0	0-0.75	0.03
			Yes	1	0.125-1	
- Cohorting employees	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	0	0-0.375	0.02
			Yes	0.5	0-1	
- Cohorting employees	Q31, Short mid solutions to maintain production: Backfill with emergency personnel from third-party companies	MW-U	No	0	0-0.5	0.02
			Yes	0.5	0-1	
- Staggered break times	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	1	0.5-1	0.05
			Yes	1	1-1	
- Staggered break times	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	0.75	0-1	0.03
			Yes	1	1-1	
- Installed physical barriers	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Major changes in operational staffing control and protection protocols	MW-U	No	0.5	0-0.5	0.006
			Yes	1	0.5-1	
Q36, Have any of these employee biosafety strategies been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?						
- Increased ventilation rates	Q31, Backfill by reorganizing personnel in the same facility	MW-U	No	0	0-0.5	0.05
			Yes	0.5	0-1	

- Air cleaning/filtering	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Implemented robotics, sensors, automation, and/or computer	MW-U	No	0.5	0-1	0.03
			Yes	1	1-1	
- Air cleaning/filtering	Q31, Backfill by reorganizing personnel in the same facility	MW-U	No	0	0-0.625	0.04
			Yes	0.5	0-1	
- Enhanced handwashing	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.79 ^c	N/A	0.03
- Alcohol-based hand rubs	Q25, Proportion (%) of employees with group transportation	SC	N/A	0.79 ^c	N/A	0.03
Q38, Have any of these surveillance strategies been applied in this facility/operation, at any point since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?						
- Contact tracing and quarantine	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	1	0.5-1	0.01
			Yes	1	1-1	
- Return to work post recovery policy	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Operations/production has expanded	MW-U	No	1	0.5-1	0.008
			Yes	1	1-1	
- Return to work post recovery policy	Q4, COVID-19 impact on industry sector: Management/corporate employees working remotely	MW-U	No	0.5	0-1	0.01
			Yes	1	1-1	
- Test for infection and isolation	Q24, Group transportation provided to employees	MW-U	No	0.5	0-1	0.01
			Yes	1	1-1	

^aLikert question (Q) number in the needs assessment survey.

^bMedian and interquartile range (IQR) calculated for the interval (1-5 in Q5, Q9, Q13, and Q29) and numeric values (0, 0.5 or 1 in Q34, Q36, and Q38) that were assigned to the Likert scale responses in each Likert item are included for comparison across facility/operation size and industry sector levels. For Q5 and Q29, values 1 to 5 represented “Not at all concerning” to “Extremely concerning”; while for Q9 and Q13, values 1 to 5 represented “Not at all important” to “Extremely important”. For Q34, Q36, and Q38, the value 0 represented “No” (not implemented), 0.5 represented “Yes, but only partially/temporarily, and 1 represented “Yes” (implemented).

^cCorrelation coefficient.

^dN/A=not applicable

^eThe original question asked about ‘50-69 years of age’ and ‘70 years or older’ but were separated here to more clearly indicate their values.